

Our community profile

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COMMUNITY OVERVIEW

[4TU.ResearchData](#) is an international data repository for science, engineering and design. The 4TU.ResearchData community was created in October 2020, and comprises researchers and research support professionals from different domains of expertise. The community provides an opportunity for members to connect and exchange knowledge about best practices for the creation and reuse of FAIR data within the technical sciences.

We're focused on...

- FAIR data and software
- Research data management
- Open Science
- Knowledge generation
- Standard setting & best practices
- Skill development
- Professional development
- Multi-stakeholder collaboration

[Visit our website](#)

84 members
+ 139 subscribers
to our [monthly newsletter](#)

Online [Community website](#) & Slack workspace

National (Netherlands) & international members

[Anyone can join.](#) Some activities are restricted to 4TU partner/member institutions

A [Community of Practice](#) where members learn & apply new skills.

WHO ARE OUR MEMBERS?

The community relies on one [community manager](#), a [technical team](#), and a growing number of active volunteers who lead community groups.

- Researcher
- Data steward
- Data manager
- Research software engineer
- Research support (other)
- Community manager

Our members are primarily from 4TU partner institutions:

- Delft University of Technology (41.3%)
- University of Twente (18.7%)
- Eindhoven University of Technology (14.7%)
- Wageningen University and Research (4.0%)
- Other institutions (6.7%)
- The 4TU.ResearchData team (14.7%)

WHAT DO WE DO TOGETHER?

ACTIVITY	FREQUENCY	OBJECTIVE	EXAMPLE	GET INVOLVED
Working groups (WG)	Monthly	To achieve specific goals and tasks with a defined scope and clear project deliverables	Participating in a WG to learn how to create and publish FAIR software code	Open to members from 4TU partner and member institutions
Special interest groups (SIG)	Ad-hoc	To explore a particular topic together which is less goal-oriented than a WG	Discussing what FAIR data means to researchers from a specific discipline	Open to all members
Focus groups (FGs)	Ad-hoc	To collect information from the community about a particular topic	Asking members for feedback about new community webpages	Open to all members
Training, events and resources	Ad-hoc	To educate community members about FAIR data practices and initiatives	Delivering a demonstration of how to upload data to 4TU.ResearchData	Open to all members (relevance depends on topic)
Community stories	Monthly	To publish stories about researchers, research data supporters and working together	Co-authoring a blog post with a researcher about their dataset to	Open to members from 4TU partner and member institutions
FAIR Data Fund	Biannual (Spring and Autumn)	To support researchers in making their data FAIR in 4TU.ResearchData	Providing financial aid for researchers to publish their datasets	Open to 4TU partner institutions
Slack workspace	Daily	To communicate, ask questions, share resources and news updates	Asking about how to integrate your GitHub account with the 4TU.ResearchData repository	Open to all members
Community calls (webinars)	Biannual (Spring and Autumn)	To learn about new topics and showcase achievements	Co-organising, attending or presenting at a community call	Open to anyone (non-members welcome)
Newsletter	Monthly	To inform about the latest news and events	Subscribing to the newsletter or contributing news	Open to anyone (non-members welcome)
Social hour	Monthly	To chat and play games	Organising a charity games night	Open to all members
Fellowship programme	Launching Spring 2020	To recruit internship students to work on FAIR data projects	Writing a series of blog posts about data stewardship	Global initiative (International students welcome)

BENEFITS FOR MEMBERS

Learn about FAIR Data and Open Science

- Attend training and events to learn and practise new skills relating to FAIR data management.
- Ask questions and seek advice about the curation, sharing, access and long-term preservation of research data.
- Receive information about funding opportunities related to FAIR Data and Open Science.
- Contribute, consult and test new services and repository features implemented by 4TU.ResearchData.

Build your network

- Meet new connections with shared interests and explore opportunities for cross-institutional collaboration.
- Work with multidisciplinary experts from diverse backgrounds, professional profiles, career stages and scientific communities.
- Co-create policies, guidelines, workflows, tools and other resources for technical science disciplines.

Boost your professional development

- Drive the development of FAIR data initiatives within your research discipline.
- Increase your impact and visibility by having your research featured on our community website and promoted via our social media channels.
- Develop your practical and interpersonal skills, and/or become a 4TU.ResearchData ambassador, to advance your career progression.

WHO CAN JOIN?

Anyone interested in FAIR data and Open Science can join the community. Currently, our members are researchers, data stewards, data managers, research software engineers, librarians, educators, IT specialists and technical experts from different domains.

HOW TO JOIN

We are working to build an inclusive community for researchers and data supporters interested in improving the creation and reuse of FAIR data within the technical sciences. If you'd like to join us, we welcome you to:

- [Join our online community](#)
[Create your public profile](#) and we'll contact you with a 'welcome pack' and an invitation to join our Slack workspace.
- [Subscribe to our newsletter](#)
Sign-up for a monthly round-up of news, events, opportunities and announcements from 4TU.ResearchData.

For more information, please contact our community manager, Connie, by email: c.e.clare@tudelft.nl